

The transitional experiences of spinal cord injury patients: Challenges, changes and coping

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 22(03), 544-551

Publication history: Received on 16 April 2025; revised on 21 June 2025; accepted on 24 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.22.3.0614>

Abstract

The objective of the study is to explore the meanings of the lived experiences of spinal cord injury patients. This research utilized qualitative husserlian phenomenological design. Semi structured interviews with six informants who had a spinal cord injury were conducted. Data was analyzed utilizing the Colaizzi process. Three themes emerged and these were: (1) Challenges of SCI patients and four sub-themes were generated: (a) financial constraints, (b) pain, (c) uncertainty of life and (d) adjusting to physical disability; (2) Changes in social support; and (3) Coping strategies which had five subthemes: (a) trying to be independent, (b) resolving to Prevail, (c) hope, (d) establishing a new Identity, and (e) psycho-spiritual upliftment. A better understanding of the meanings ascribed to the lived experiences of SCI patients can guide the family, healthcare professionals and future researchers to develop responsive approaches to support these patients.

Keywords: Spinal Cord Injury patients; Qualitative study; Husserlian phenomenology

1. Introduction

The spinal cord is the most important structure connecting the brain with the rest of the body. It extends from the foramen magnum, where it is continuous with the medulla, to the level of the first or second lumbar vertebrae. It is a vital link carrying nerves that convey incoming and outgoing messages between the brain and the body (Dafny, 2018). Spinal cord injury (SCI) is a medically complex and life-disrupting condition that has historically been associated with very high mortality rates. Patients with SCI experience numerous physical, psychological, and social challenges. These difficulties—including limitations in performing common self-care activities and disruptions to individual and occupational responsibilities—can also impose significant emotional, psychological, economic, and environmental stress on both the patient and family. Coping with these stressors often requires a transition from an independent life to one of greater dependence, which in turn necessitates a redefinition and reassessment of one's social and occupational roles (Song, 2018).

SCI rehabilitation is a specialty area that relies heavily on an interdisciplinary team of physicians, nurses, psychologists, therapists, and nutritionists to provide optimal care. This process requires thorough medical management during the acute phase followed by comprehensive rehabilitation that includes physical, bowel, bladder, and skin management, health education, counseling, vocational training, and long-term follow-up (Hans, 2019).

Nurses play a vital role in caring for persons with SCI throughout the acute care, rehabilitation, and community settings. In addition to providing psychosocial support, discharge planning, and collaborating with other caregivers, nurses are instrumental in educating patients and families about the physiologic changes that result from spinal cord injury.

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Architectural barriers, along with social, family, and psychological adjustments required when returning home, underscore the importance of reintegration support (Nelson, 2018).

Because SCI patients often require extensive assistance with self-care due to immobilization, nurses must frequently check on patients, assist with mobilization, and provide education on self-management.

This study explored the lived experiences of spinal cord injury patients from the perspective of those who have experienced such events. Their day-to-day experiences were examined to understand the phenomenon of SCI as it unfolds in real life.

A gap in qualitative research exists regarding personal experiences of SCI patients in the Philippines—particularly in Cebu City—which further justifies the need for this study.

Objective of the Study

The study explored the lived experiences of patients with spinal cord injury in Cebu City, Philippines.

Significance of the Study

This study contributes to a better understanding of SCI by documenting and analyzing patients' lived experiences. The findings offer insights into the challenges associated with debilitating injuries and have the potential to contribute to improved patient care, nursing practice, education, and future research.

2. Review of related literature and studies

Spinal cord injuries (SCI) are life-altering not only for the person injured but also for their family and friends. The lack of effective treatments to repair neurological dysfunctions below the injury level means that many victims experience long-term loss of independence and incur ongoing medical expenses. SCI can cause devastating disability and complications affecting multiple body systems (Ali & Tawfiq, 2019).

Individuals with SCI undergo a process of physical and mental adaptation in the early years following injury and must overcome numerous barriers to achieve a satisfactory quality of life (Noreau, 2018).

SCI typically causes immediate, often permanent, loss of muscle function and sensation below the injury level, as well as impairments in bowel and bladder function and sexual health. These conditions usually require significant assistance with activities of daily living (Charlifue, 2019).

Other organ systems may be affected as well. For example, injuries to the upper thoracic and cervical spine can compromise respiratory function, and lack of adequate musculature may lead to ineffective coughing. Moreover, disuse osteoporosis develops rapidly after SCI, increasing the risk for pathologic fractures (Garland, 2018).

In the acute phase, SCI results in autonomic and somatic nervous system dysfunction that can lead to secondary complications over time. Such complications may eventually compromise the patient's independence and necessitate ongoing external support (Eastwood, 2017).

The sudden loss resulting from SCI creates new lifestyle challenges. Early studies identified depression as a common and critical element in the grieving and adjustment process following SCI. Patients often grieve the loss of their previous body, activities, and lifestyle, which can lead to a post-bereavement depressive state (Kennedy & Rogers, 2019).

Langer (2018) noted that clinical depression following SCI may stem from the process of grieving the loss of the former self, with responses including sadness, bitterness, anger, and shock.

Other research indicates that what appears as major depression after SCI might partly be a coping process; some patients use excessive medication or even street drugs to numb the pain associated with their injury (Gill, 2018).

Spinal cord injury not only presents physical challenges but also imposes psychosocial ramifications. Many individuals experience decreased self-esteem and self-efficacy due to increased dependency, which may lead to a cascade of negative outcomes such as dependency, depression, drug addiction, and even divorce (Gill, 2018).

In one study of SCI rehabilitation, interactions with staff were observed to affect patients' self-identity. Disrespectful attitudes and behaviors from staff can compromise a patient's sense of individuality and dignity, leading to feelings of powerlessness and depression. Facilitating self-directed behavior through increased patient choice and control was suggested as an empowering strategy (Samuel & Moses, 2018).

Another study on the meaning of context in recapturing self-care after SCI reported that changes in the lived body lead to changes in a person's life-world, as self-perception is rooted in bodily experience. In understanding self-care after SCI, it is essential to consider both individual perceptions and the broader social contexts in which daily life is carried out (Susanne & Kerstin, 2018).

Rehabilitation programs generally focus on training patients in self-care skills through occupational and physical therapies and health education. One phenomenological study in Japan found that in early rehabilitation, patients internalize a notion of self-care that is influenced by family responsibilities, with the family playing a major role in meeting self-care needs. In time, patients begin to personalize their bodies as they reengage socially (Ayako & Etsuko, 2019).

Adaptation to SCI is a dynamic process that unfolds over time. Factors such as a history of substance abuse, limited social support, low self-esteem, a dysfunctional family, or lack of spirituality can hinder coping. Successful adaptation is often associated with faith in a higher power, robust social and emotional support, and a strong desire for independence (Gill, 2018).

A study on Iranian SCI patients found that common coping strategies include acceptance, seeking information, positive reframing, minimization, self-trust, optimism, and positive thinking. Spirituality and religiousness further facilitated coping by providing a framework for meaning-making and emotional support (Babamohamadi, 2017).

Resilience in the face of SCI is strongly linked to spirituality, which may manifest as prayer, meditation, or other forms of faith-based practice. Enhanced spiritual well-being is associated with improved emotional support and resilience (Hodges, 2018).

Bowers (2018) discussed the developmental nature of spirituality in the rehabilitation journey, suggesting that the onset of illness or disability can catalyze spiritual growth through a sequence of developmental stages. Another study described disability as a formative experience that prompts spiritual growth by challenging individuals to reconsider concepts of control and purpose in life. Spirituality, with its past, present, and future dimensions, can help individuals reconcile loss and foster a sense of meaning (Ross, 2018).

Research on social support in SCI shows that immediately following injury, patients rely on others for physical assistance. Over time, however, the nature of support shifts toward promoting independent self-care. Early physical support gives way to the psychological comfort of simply having someone nearby (Anson, Stanwyck, & Krause, 2018).

Nelson (2018) emphasized the importance of facilitating clients' progression through acceptance stages during rehabilitation. Community-based resocialization efforts can help reduce the stigma of disability and support the patient's reintegration into society.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological design based on Husserlian phenomenology. According to Husserl, consciousness is the pathway to accessing the material world. His method—encompassing intentionality, phenomenological reduction, description, and essence—requires that the researcher set aside preconceptions to capture the pure essence of experience (Wojnar, 2018).

Husserl argued that through careful, theory-free observation, one can reveal the essential structures of experience that include truth, certainty, and objectivity—qualities that are foundational to scientific inquiry. This qualitative approach enabled the researcher to gain detailed insights into the actual experiences of spinal cord injury patients (Marshall, 2018).

The phenomenological approach was chosen because its purpose is to describe and understand the essence of lived experiences of individuals who have undergone a particular phenomenon (Litchman, 2018).

3.2. Research Locale

The study was conducted in Cebu City, Philippines. It was community-based, with participants recruited from various barangays, and interviews were conducted in their respective homes.

3.3. Research Informants and Sampling Technique

Key informants were SCI patients residing in Cebu City. A purposive homogeneous sampling technique was used to select participants who met specific eligibility criteria. A sample of six key informants was recruited, and pseudonyms were used to protect their identities.

3.3.1. Participant Profiles

Darmian is a 26 year old single male residing in Cebu City. He is not currently employed. He and his fiancée were enjoying a day-off at a friend's house. He attempted to jump in the pool accidentally he slipped and fell on his head and broke his neck before sinking to the bottom. Soon after, he learned that he injured his C4 and C5 vertebrae and spinal cord resulting in paralysis in the majority of his body.

Bastian is 19 year old single male from Cebu city. He is unemployed. He fell from a coconut tree after a misstep that rendered paralyzed both arms and legs.

Eva is 26 years old and she was involved in a car accident in her hometown. Her C5 vertebra was fractured resulting in loss of sensory and motor function in her legs and very little function in her arms and hands.

Sergio is a 29 year old male a resident of Cebu city. He was always athletic, which is why he had the privilege to join the Philippine military as an army officer. He was often training with friends around the base. One afternoon, he was out riding his bicycle near army barracks when a truck driver lost control and hit him from behind, ejecting him from his bike, breaking his neck, and injuring his spinal cord. The accident left him paralyzed from the waist down.

Anthony a 22 year old young man was one time riding a motorbike of his friend on their way from school. They were hit from behind by a drunk driver who was speeding and he injured his spinal cord

Maria is a 28 year old lady. A few years ago after an evening of celebrating her birthday at a night club with friends and on the way home she was hit by a drunk driver while walking across the street. This devastating life-altering accident left her paralyzed both arms and legs.

3.4. Research Instrument and Procedures

A semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions was used (see Appendix B). Direct observation and field notes supplemented the narrative data. Informed consent was obtained from all informants prior to the interviews. The researcher engaged in bracketing to minimize bias, and a pilot interview was conducted prior to the full study. Interviews lasted approximately two hours (with breaks), were audio-recorded, and conducted in settings convenient to the participants.

3.5. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Colaizzi's (1978) method for phenomenological data analysis. This process involved transcribing interviews, validating transcriptions with participants, extracting significant statements, formulating meanings, clustering these meanings into themes, and validating the findings with participants.

Figure 1 A summary of Colaizzi's strategy for data analysis [Shosha, 2010]

3.6. Role of Investigator

The investigator ensured availability during scheduled interviews and safeguarded the rights and freedoms of the clients. Immersion in the philosophy of descriptive phenomenology helped prepare the researcher for in-depth data collection.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

Informants were fully informed of the study's purpose and procedures, and their participation was voluntary. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study, and all data were securely disposed of after the thesis defense.

4. Results

4.1. Thematic Analysis

Data analysis yielded 90 significant statements, 45 formulated meanings, 9 subthemes, and three main themes:

4.2. Challenges of SCI Patients

Financial Constraints: High costs of treatment and rehabilitation cause significant stress. One informant stated, "Everybody needs help at some point, I spend a lot of money for my treatment and therapy sessions and it has become too costly" (Maria, SS12).

Pain: The severity of pain often prevents routine activities. For example, "The pain was just too much for me to handle. I wouldn't just make any movement because at any given moment if I moved I would feel the pain" (Maria, SS13).

Uncertainty of Life: Concerns about long-term disability and future quality of life were common (Darmian, SS2; Maria, SS1; Sergio, SS15).

Adjusting to Physical Disability: Participants described a struggle to reconcile their internal self-image with their externally changed bodies (Bastian, SS1; Maria, SS16).

4.3. Changes in Social Support

Family, friends, and caregivers played a crucial role in motivating and supporting SCI patients. As one participant noted, "My family has been the best gift in this journey. They have been there with me since I got this injury" (Anthony, SS9). The shift in support—from physical assistance to enabling more independent self-care—was also highlighted (Eva, SS6).

4.4. Coping Strategies

Coping strategies included efforts to regain independence, maintain hope, establish a new identity, and pursue psycho-spiritual upliftment. For instance, one participant explained, "I accepted walker and brace easily. Perhaps at first my motivation was not to build up my problems, but to get more independence" (Eva, SS7). Other strategies included setting achievable objectives and relying on spiritual faith (Anthony, SS7; Eva, SS5).

5. Discussion

The study's findings confirm that SCI poses significant financial, physical, and emotional challenges. Many participants reported difficulties in managing treatment costs and experiencing chronic pain. The uncertainty of future independence was a recurring theme, while social support—from family, peers, and rehabilitation staff—proved essential for recovery and self-care.

Peer interactions, as noted in previous research, can foster a positive appraisal of SCI and contribute to more effective coping strategies (King, 2018). The findings also underscore the importance of individualized support and the need for health professionals, particularly nurses and occupational therapists, to tailor care plans to each patient's unique needs (Tham, 2018).

Religious and spiritual coping emerged as a significant factor in how patients managed their conditions. As observed by Udermann (2018), regular participation in spiritual practices may enhance healing capabilities. However, these findings contrast with Pollard and Kennedy's (2018) earlier observation that religious strategies might diminish over time. Additionally, hope was identified as a critical motivator, consistent with research by Lohne and Severinsson (2018). Finally, efforts to regain independence—whether through returning to work or adapting daily routines—were seen as key to enhancing self-esteem and overall quality of life (Anderson, Dumont, & Azzaria, 2018).

An exhaustive description of the phenomenon was developed by synthesizing the themes and validating them with the participants.

6. Conclusion

The study concludes that SCI involves complex challenges—physical, emotional, and financial—that require patients to adapt to new lifestyles. Although SCI imposes significant hardships, the findings suggest that with appropriate social, emotional, and rehabilitative support, patients can develop effective coping strategies. This underscores the importance of integrating individualized spiritual, psychosocial, and self-care interventions into patient care.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Relatives and caregivers should be educated on addressing the physical manifestations of SCI with sensitivity.
- Healthcare professionals should emphasize the provision of psychosocial support to enhance patients' self-care agency and overall well-being.
- Nurses are encouraged to facilitate individualized spiritual coping by allowing time and space for religious activities.
- To promote effective coping and improve quality of care, nurses should assess individual patient challenges and coping mechanisms to develop tailored care plans.
- SCI patients and their significant others should be provided with favorable environmental conditions and opportunities to interact with peers facing similar challenges, as such interactions may positively influence emotional adjustment and rehabilitation outcomes.
- The findings of this study may be used by SCI patients and their families to better understand the challenges associated with spinal cord injury.

- Further qualitative research into the phenomenology of SCI experiences is recommended in various settings across the Philippines.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

We declare No conflict of interest

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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